

Purification of the fusion protein QQ02ACVR2A and the protein FKBP12. Complex formation of the two and subsequent crystallisation with crystal condition optimisation.

Rationale:

ACVR2A, Alk3 and Alk6 are structurally similar to Alk2 and thus a crystal structure of any of these with the M4KPharma compounds of interest would be of use for future drug development.

Aim:

Purify QQ02ACVR2A and FKBP1AA (AKA FKBP12) as a complex for use in crystallography studies.

Proteins to be purified:

QQ02ACVR2A-c001

SMP LQLLEVKARGRFGCVWKAQLLNEYVAVKIFPIQDKQSWQNEYEVYSLPGMKHENILQFIGAEKRGTSVDVDL
WLITAFHEKGSLSDFLKANVVSWNELCHIAETMARGLAYLHEDIPGLKDGHKPAISHRDIKSKNVLLKNNLTACIADF
GLALKFEAGKSAGDTHGQVGTTRRYMAPEVLEGAINFQRDAFLRIDMYAMGLVLWELASRCTAADGPVDEYMLPF
EEEIGQHPSLEDMQEVVHKKRVPVRDYWQKHAGMAMLCETIEECWDHDAEARLSAGCVGERITQMQRLTNI
GGNAGGNAGGNAGGNASMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGS
WQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGS LYDYQLTTLDT
VSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTK
RYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFD SYKRVDIWAFLVLWEVARRMVSN GIVEDYKPPFYD VVPNDPSFEDMRKVVCDQ
QRPNIPNRWFSDPTLTSLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKTLTKID

FKBP1AA-c001 (N-terminal GST tag)

SMGVQVETISPGDGRTPKRGQTCVVHYTGMLEDGKKFDSSRDRNKPFKFM LGKQEVIRGWEEGVAQMSVGQ
RAKLTISPDYAYGATGHPGIIPPHATLVFDVELLKE

Expression:

FKBP1AA was expressed in E.coli, 10ml of overnight in Kan+ media was used to inoculate 1l LB. Cells were grown at 37C until induction by 0.4mM IPTG at OD 0.7. Cells were grown overnight at 18C and harvested at 5000rpm and stored at -20. QQ02ACVR2A was expressed in Sf9 insect cells by Shubash at 27°C for 72 hours in glass shaker flasks.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice for baculo cells. 5min on time for E.coli cells.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

SDS-PAGE gel of Nickle purification of FKBP12 and QQ02ACVR2A showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions. The red box indicates samples taken on for additional purification.

- Pool elution fractions as shown above.
- Add Tev protease to fractions which contain protein
- Concentrate down boxed samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column for FKBP12 and GF 200 column for QQ02ACVR2A using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

- Mix QQ02ACVR2A with a four fold excess of FKBP12. Concentrate down to <5ml and run on a GF 200 size exclusion column to isolate any complex formed.

SDS-PAGE gel of gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF200 size exclusion column. The red box indicates the samples taken forward for use. Bands for both QQ02ACVR2A and FKBP12 can be seen to co-purify

Crystallography:

- Concentrate protein down to 11mg/ml
- Add compound K02288 at 1mM concentration.
- Spin for 10 minutes at 14,000 rpm to remove precipitant
- Set up crystal plates using coarse screens as follows:

Single sized drops (150nl), 3 drop ratio (1:2, 2:2, 2:1)

Bar code	Screen	Additives	Comments:
CI073059	HIN3	K02288	4C
CI073058	BCS2	K02288	20C
CI073039	HCS3	K02288	4C
CI073038	LFS6	K02288	20C

Crystals observed in HCS plate:

HCS3

B6

A8

A7

Crystalline material seen in the following wells o HCS3.

B6: 20% PEG8000, 0.2M Mg Acetate, 0.1M Cacodylate pH6.5

A7: 1.4M Na Acetate, 0.1M Cacodylate pH6.5

A8: 30% 2-propanol, 0.2M Na Citrate tribasic, 0.1M Cacodylate pH6.5

Followup plate designed to optimise these conditions:

HCS3-B6_A7_A8_ew-z001												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
B	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
C	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.1M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.2M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.3M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC	0.4M MgAC
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
D	1M NAAC	1M NAAC	1M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.4M NAAC	1.4M NAAC	1.4M NAAC	1.6M NAAC	1.6M NAAC	1.6M NAAC
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
E	1M NAAC	1M NAAC	1M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.2M NAAC	1.4M NAAC	1.4M NAAC	1.6M NAAC	1.6M NAAC	1.6M NAAC	1.6M NAAC
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
F	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
G	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											
H	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.1M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.2M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.3M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT	0.4M NaCIT
	16% PEG8K	18% PEG8K	20% PEG8K	22% PEG8K	20% 2PROH	25% 2PROH	30% 2PROH	35% 2PROH	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl	0.1M cacodyl
	0.1M cacodyl											

FU chemical screen for complex crystallisation

2 Plates set up in this follow-up screen at 4°C and 20°C. Setup protocol was the same as described above. The following crystals appeared after 7 days at 4°C. They were mounted and taken to Diamond. No diffraction observed.

Crystals mounted of QQ02ACVR2/FKBP12 complex from followup screen.